

CORPORATE VALUE CREATION THROUGH BUYBACK ANNOUNCEMENT -- EARNINGS PER SHARE AND STOCK PRICE ANALYSES

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ABSTRACT

The objective of the paper is to examine whether buyback announcement increases earnings per share and stock price to create the value for the shareholders. The sample size of the paper consists of 71 and 62 initial buyback programs of listed companies for earnings per share and stock price analyses respectively announced during the period from 1998 to 2013. The earnings per share and stock price are compared for consecutive two years both before and after the announcement of buyback. A large sample t – test has been conducted to test whether increase and decrease in the EPS and the stock price are statistically significant. The paper finds that the announcement of stock buyback signals increase in the earnings per share and stock price.

Keywords: EPS, t-test, buyback, shareholders, Corporate Value.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of a profit oriented company is to earn profit for the shareholders. The increase in the profit of the company causes increase in the earnings per share and rise in the stock price of the company. The increase in the earnings per share and the stock price of the company creates value for the shareholders. However, now, it is difficult for the company to create shareholder value by maintaining the profit or improving the earnings due to a number of market constraints like lack of demand, intensified competition, falling market share, saturated market, etc. Therefore, the companies, these days, adopt different financial strategies to create the value for the shareholders. Some of the widely used financial strategies to restructure the capital structure and the capitalization of the company and to enhance the value of the shareholders imply buyback of equity, stock splits, etc.. These non-operational and readjusting the capital structure

financial strategies produce the desired results if they are adopted and used properly in time by the good and financially strong companies. Therefore, the present paper, concentrates on the corporate value creation through buyback of equity in order to examine whether buyback of equity increases the earnings per share and the stock price and thereby create the value for the shareholders.

METHODOLOGY

The objective of the paper is to examine whether buyback announcement increases earnings per share and stock price to create the value for the shareholders. The sample size of the paper consists of 71 and 62 initial buyback programs of listed companies for EPS and stock price analyses respectively announced during the period from 1998 to 2013.. The paper chooses the comparison period from 1998 to 2015. The EPS in the year of buyback and the stock price on the day of buyback are compared respectively with the EPS and the stock price for the consecutive two years both before and after the announcement and the EPS and the stock price after the announcement of buyback are compared with the EPS and the stock price respectively before the announcement in order to find out the number companies showing the increase and decrease in the EPS and the stock price. A large sample t – test has been conducted to test whether number of companies showing the increase and decrease in the EPS and the stock price is statistically significant.

A further research work can be carried on corporate value creation through buyback announcement – earnings per share and stock price analyses with a comparison period of more than two years, with a larger sample size and on subsequent buyback programs.

Review of Literature on Buyback of Shares

The literature on buyback of shares has been reviewed chronologically in the following;
Dielman, et. all (1980) studied the stock behavior of 174 repurchases of 139 firms during 1957 to 1974 by way of open market and through tender offer. They employed regression model and found that i) open market repurchases have no economic significance i.e., repurchase effects on rates of return are uniformly negligible and in respect of tender offer, repurchase is associated with significant increase in return in the month of announcement and ii) announcing a buyback is announcing to the market that the firm has run out of profitable investment opportunities. This implies a negative relationship between buyback and stock price.

Vermaelen (1981) studied 131 tender offer announcements during the years 1962 to 1977. He found that i) unless the percentage of shares tendered by the share holders is exactly equal to the percentage of shares purchased by the company, the expected price to prevail after the buyback will always be lower than the offer price, ii) it will be incorrect to use share price increase after the announcement as a measure of the value change per share resulting from the tender offer, iii) signaling effect can explain most of the value increase due to buyback in the US i.e., evidence of

about 16% value increase after share buyback in the US and iv) debt financed buybacks have got a higher impact on the stock price (24%) as compared to cash financed buybacks(18%) in the US.

Neena Puri (2001) analyzed 14 buyback programs announced by the listed companies in India from 1999 to 2001. She found that only 2 out of the 14 companies which came up with buyback offers have been successful in having the desired effect of achieving superior share price performance and returns for the shareholders. She concludes that the result of the study goes against the commonly held belief that the buyback of shares is accompanied by an increase in the share price.

Pitabas Mohanty (2002) analyzed share buyback of 12 companies during the period from 1999 to 2001. The study finds that i) stock prices do move up because of the high offer premium only to fall back to their original level , ii) buyback does not result in any perceptible long run increase in the value and iii) evidence of insider trading before the share buyback is announced.

Karamjeet Kaur and Balwinder Singh (2003) analyzed 77 buyback programs announced by 60 companies during 1999-2003. They used comparison period returns approach to study the response of the stock market to the announcement of buyback programs. They found that the buyback announcements are associated with positive returns considering the stock markets to be fairly efficient. This can be attributed to informational asymmetries between managers and investors. The study concludes that the companies are able to successfully achieve their motive of correcting the undervaluation of stock and signaling their future prospects.

A.K. Mishra (2005) studied 25 buyback programs by different companies over the period from 1999-2001. He finds a favorable reaction around the announcement date. He concludes that i) stock price reaction to buyback is temporary and buybacks could not ensure a sustained rise in the price of the scrip, ii) there is no favorable effect of buyback on EPS as out of total 25 companies only 11 companies registered enhancement in the EPS and iii) buyback price has no correlation with the fair valuation of the share.

Amitabh Gupta (2006) examined 46 buyback of shares made by listed companies during the period 1999-2004.. His research study found that the announcement of share buyback significantly increases the share price around the time of the announcement.

Pournima Jariwala (2011) examined buyback of 82 companies through open market repurchase in India over the period from 2000 to 2009.. She employed Mean price to study the movement of the stock price and Ratio analysis to measure the operating performance before and after the announcement of buyback. She found that i) share price, generally, on an average, react positively to buyback announcement, ii) share buyback signals increase in the operating

efficiency in the future and iii) stock buyback creates value for shareholders. She concludes that there should be strict regulations disallowing the companies to make the fresh issue of shares at least for one year after buyback and thereby to avoid manipulation in the share price.

Research Gap

The research studies in the past have examined earnings per share and signaling hypotheses in order to identify the impact of stock buyback on the EPS and the stock price for a maximum comparison period of 1 year before and 1 year after the announcement. These studies have found that there is no effect of buyback on the EPS while the announcement buyback increases the stock price on and around the announcement day. The present study therefore adopts earnings per share and signaling hypotheses with a comparison period of 2 years before and 2 years after the announcement so as to examine the impact of the buyback announcement on the EPS and the stock price for a period of more than one year in order to ascertain whether buyback announcement create perceptible long run value for the shareholders.

EARNINGS PER SHARE ANALYSIS

An Earnings per share is one of the tools of measuring the operational efficiency of the company. When a company buys back its own equity shares, the number of outstanding shares decreases and the earnings per share increases. This does not indicate the improvement in either earnings or earnings per share because when the number of outstanding shares decreases, the earnings per share has to increase. Therefore, in this paper, the earnings per share of the company in the year of buyback is compared with the earnings per share for the consecutive two years both before and after the announcement of buyback in order to ascertain whether announcement of stock buyback signals increase in the earnings and earnings per share of the company.

Analysis And Interpretation Of Earnings Per Share Of Buyback Companies

The earnings per share of buyback companies are analyzed and interpreted for the consecutive two years both before and after the announcement in order to find out whether stock buyback signals increase in the earnings per share of the company. The following tables show the number of companies showing increase and decrease in the earnings per share and the test statistics at 5% and 1% level of significance;

Table No.1.a: No. of Companies showing increase and decrease in the earnings per share for different periods surrounding the announcement of buyback

Sample Companies – 71

Sr. No.	Period	Increase		Decrease	
		No. of Companies	%	No. of Companies	%
1	EPSOYAABB to EPSYABB (> and <)	39	55	32	45
2	EPSTYAABB to EPSYABB (> and <)	35	49	36	51
3	EPSYABB to EPSOYBABB (> AND <)	47	66	24	34
4	EPSYABB to EPSTYBABB (> and <)	47	66	24	34
5	EPSOYAABB to EPSOYBABB (> and <)	48	68	23	32
6	EPSTYAABB to EPSTYBABB (> and <)	46	65	25	35
7	AEPSAABB to AEPSBABB (> and <)	49	69	22	31

Table No.1.b : (Test Statistics) - Number of Companies showing increase and decrease in the Earnings per Share

Sr. No.				Test statistics	Conclusion at 5% LS	Conclusion at 1% LS
1	Period	EPSOYAABB	EPSYABB	1.284	No significant difference found	No significant difference found
	Mean	16.13	18.92			
	SD	16.38	22.59			
2	Period	EPSTYAABB	EPSYABB	1.696	No significant difference found	No significant difference found
	Mean	15.62	18.89			
	SD	19.33	22.57			
3	Period	EPSYABB	EPSOYBABB	2.162	Reject	No significant difference found
	Mean	18.89	14.10			
	SD	22.57	16.37			
4	Period	EPSYABB	EPSTYBABB	2.787	Reject	Reject
	Mean	18.89	12.27			
	SD	22.57	15.75			
5	Period	EPSOYAABB	EPSOYBABB	1.136	No significant difference found	No significant difference found
	Mean	16.13	14.10			
	SD	16.38	16.37			
6	Period	EPSTYAABB	EPSTYBABB	1.681	No significant difference found	No significant difference found
	Mean	15.62	12.27			
	SD	19.33	15.75			
7	Period	AEPSAABB	AEPSBABB	1.644	No significant difference found	No significant difference found
	Mean	15.92	13.18			
	SD	16.78	15.56			

The tables 1.a and 2.b indicate the following;

- 1) There is a significant increase in the earnings per share in the year of announcement of buyback as compared to the earnings per share one year before the announcement at 5% level of significance.
- 2) The earnings per share in the year of announcement of buyback increased significantly at 1% level of significance over the earnings per share two years before the announcement.
- 3) There is no significant increase in the earnings per share one year and two years after the announcement of buyback as against the earnings per share in the year of announcement. This indicates that the buyback does not signal improvement in the earnings and operational efficiency of the company in the future.
- 4) The earnings per share and average earnings per share after the announcement of buyback do not increase significantly as compared to the earnings per share and average earnings per share before the announcement.

Findings

The announcement of buyback of shares indicates an increase in the earnings per share of the company. However, it does not signal either increase in the earnings or improvement in the operational efficiency of the company in the future. The finding of the paper on the earnings per share contradicts the findings of Mishra, A. K. (2005) and similarly, the findings on earnings and operational efficiency in the future contradict the findings of Jariwala, Pournima (2011).

STOCK PRICE ANALYSIS

The performance of the company reflects on the share price. Sometimes, the fundamentals of the company are good but the share price does not do well in the market. In this situation, the company may announce the stock buyback to signal the undervaluation of stock and better prospects for the company in the future. If the company announces the buyback of equity, the stock price of the company moves upward. The rise in the stock price results in the capital appreciation and the capital gains to the shareholders. This ensures the abnormal returns to the shareholders. The paper, hence, makes an attempt to compare the stock price after the announcement of buyback with the stock price before the announcement for the consecutive two years so as to find out whether announcement of buyback increases the stock price.

Analysis and Interpretation of Stock Price of Buyback Companies

The number of companies showing increase and decrease in the mean stock price and the test statistics at 5% and 1% level of significance are shown in the following tables;

Table No. 2.a: No. of Companies showing increase and decrease in the stock k price for different periods surrounding the announcement of buyback - Sample Companies—62

Sr. No.	Period	Increase		Decrease	
		No. of Companies	%	No. of Companies	%
1	SPSMAABB to SPOTDABB (> and <)	39	63	23	37
2	SPOYAABB to SPOTDABB (> and <)	39	63	23	37
3	SPOHYAABB to SPOTDABB (> and <)	39	63	23	37
4	SPTYAABB to SPOTDABB (> and <)	40	65	22	35
5	SPOTDABB to SPSMBABB (> and <)	30	48	32	52
6	SPOTDABB to SPOYBABB (> and <)	30	48	32	52
7	SPOTDABB to SPOHYBABB (> and <)	28	45	34	55
8	SPOTDABB to SPTYBABB (> and <)	27	44	35	56
9	SPSMAABB to SPSMBABB (> and <)	35	56	27	44
10	SPOYAABB to SPOYBABB (> and <)	33	53	29	47
11	SPOHYAABB to SPOHYBABB (> and <)	32	52	30	48
12	SPTYAABB to SPTYBABB (> and <)	34	55	28	45

Table No. 2.b (Test Statistics) : Number of Companies showing increase and decrease in the Stock Price

Sr. No.				Test statistics	Conclusion at 5% LS	Conclusion at 1% LS
1	Period	SPSMAABB	SPOTDABB	1.544	No significant difference found	No significant difference found
	Mean	162.50	148.63			
	SD	183.254	150.344			
2	Period	SPOYAABB	SPOTDABB	2.193	Reject	No significant difference found
	Mean	174.13	148.63			
	SD	192.599	150.344			
3	Period	SPOHYAABB	SPOTDABB	2.753	Reject	Reject
	Mean	185.95	148.63			

	SD	203.593	150.344			
4	Period	SPTYAABB	SPOTDABB	3.206	Reject	Reject
	Mean	195.16	148.63			
	SD	210.958	150.344			
5	Period	SPOTDABB	SPSMBABB	2.023	Reject	No significant difference found
	Mean	148.63	163.84			
	SD	150.344	166.326			
6	Period	SPOTDABB	SPOYBABB	2.537	Reject	No significant difference found
	Mean	148.63	176.13			
	SD	150.344	188.574			
7	Period	SPOTDABB	SPOHYBABB	2.548	Reject	No significant difference found
	Mean	148.63	183.69			
	SD	150.344	203.860			
8	Period	SPOTDABB	SPTYBABB	2.630	Reject	No significant difference found
	Mean	148.63	181.85			
	SD	150.344	191.212			
9	Period	SPSMAABB	SPSMBABB	0.143	No significant difference found	No significant difference found
	Mean	157.81	159.15			
	SD	182.202	165.856			
10	Period	SPOYAABB	SPOYBABB	0.184	No significant difference found	No significant difference found
	Mean	169.12	170.98			
	SD	191.600	187.798			
11	Period	SPOHYAABB	SPOHYBABB	0.188	No significant difference found	No significant difference found
	Mean	180.51	178.30			
	SD	202.575	202.962			
12	Period	SPTYAABB	SPTYBABB	0.935	No significant difference found	No significant difference found
	Mean	189.45	176.47			
	SD	210.055	190.540			

The Table Nos. 2.a and 2.b depict the following;

- 1) The stock price significantly increased at 1% level of significance after the announcement of buyback as compared to the stock price on the day of the announcement.
- 2) There is no significant increase in the stock price on the day of the announcement of buyback as against the stock price before the announcement.
- 3) The mean stock price after the announcement of buyback does not increase significantly as compared to the mean stock price before the announcement.

FINDINGS

There is an increase in the stock price after the announcement of buyback as against the stock price on the day of the announcement while, on the contrary, there is no significant increase in the stock price after the announcement of buyback as compared to the stock price before the announcement. The announcement of the stock buyback, therefore, signals an increase in the stock price and undervaluation of stock. The findings of the study on the stock price analysis are similar with the findings of the study conducted by Mohanty, Pitabas (2002), Kaur, Karamjeet and Singh, Balwinder (2003), Gupta, Amitabh (2006) and Jariwala, Pournima (2011) and contradict the research findings of Dielman et.all (1980), Vermaelen (1981) and Puri, Neena (2001).

CONCLUSION

The announcement of stock buyback signals increase in the earnings per share and the stock price of the company. However, it does not indicate the improvement in the earnings and operational efficiency of the company. Therefore, it can be concluded that the announcement of buyback of equity increases the earnings per share and the stock price of the company and thereby creates the value for the shareholders.

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